

Defining Strategic Environmental Goals and Objectives for the Management of Deep-Sea Mining Operations in the Seabed Beyond National Jurisdiction

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Executive summary: After the inconclusive 2nd part of the 28th Annual Session of the International Seabed Authority (ISA) in July 2023, there were concerns that ISA would start accepting exploitation applications for deep-sea mining with neither a full regulatory framework in place nor a general policy related to the conservation of our marine environment. At this time, the environmental management of deep-sea mining by ISA is cursory and lacks strategic aims regarding the preservation of deep-sea ecosystems. This makes ISA unable to fulfill its environmental stewardship mandate as defined in the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea. To overcome this inability, we propose that ISA needs to define Strategic Environmental Goals and Objectives by carrying out a Strategic Environmental Assessment of deep-sea mining across all regions, with broader stakeholder engagement and considerations for cumulative and long-term effects. This will allow ISA to develop the first strategic environmental policy for the Area under its jurisdiction to protect deep-sea ecosystems.

I. Environmental stewardship mandate of the International Seabed Authority

The International Seabed Authority (ISA) is an international organization responsible for managing activities related to mineral resources in the seabed beyond national jurisdictions (the Area). ISA was created in 1994 by stipulation of the United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) and the Part IX Implementation Agreement and has been in operation since 1996. UNCLOS mandates ISA to, on behalf of humankind as a whole, administer the mineral resources located in the Area, which are the common heritage of humankind, in whom the rights to such resources are invested (UNCLOS, Art. 140, 157(1)).

Although the exploitation of mineral resources in the Area may generate economic benefits for humankind, the best available scientific knowledge about the environmental consequences of deep-sea mining indicates that mining activities in the Area have direct impacts on deep-sea ecosystems in the forms of species removal, community changes, degradation of habitats and biodiversity loss (Gollner et al. 2017; Jones et al. 2019). Due to the triggering of the “two-year rule”¹ by the Republic of Nauru in 2021 and a contractor’s intention to submit a mining exploitation application as early as July 2024 (The Metals Company 2023), ISA urgently needs to

¹ The “two-year rule” is a provision of the Part XI Agreement (Section 1(15) of the Annex) that allows a Member State to request that the ISA Council complete the exploitation regulations within two years. If the Council fails to complete the regulations in this time frame and an application for exploitation is submitted, the Council has to consider and provisionally approve the application.

adopt strategic goals for the protection of the environment before these negative environmental impacts become a reality. In addition, UNCLOS requires that the marine environment shall be effectively protected from mining activities in the Area (UNCLOS, Art. 145). This adds another layer of urgency to develop a thorough plan to protect the marine environment and deep-sea ecosystems if any mining activities are to be allowed.

However, ISA currently lacks a proper tool to manage the environmental responsibilities entailed by its environmental stewardship mandate (Jaeckel 2020; Blanchard et al. 2023). Considering the known impacts, risks, and uncertainties involved in ISA's mandate to protect the deep-sea environment, a strategic approach to environmental management is urgently needed (Jaeckel 2020).

II. Status of environmental stewardship in ISA

To manage the seabed minerals-related operations in the Area, ISA is developing a set of rules, regulations, and procedures collectively known as the Mining Code. As part of the Mining Code, ISA has developed a regional environmental management policy based on Area-Based Management Tools (Blanchard and Gollner 2022). In particular, Regulations 44 and 44 bis of Part IV of Draft Exploitation Regulations address Regional Environmental Management Plans (REMPs) as providers of region-specific tools to ensure the effective protection of marine environments (Levin, Amon, and Lily 2020; Ginzky, Singh, and Markus 2020; Blanchard et al. 2023). As an example of this regional approach to environmental management, the Clarion-Clipperton Zone REMF in the Northeast Pacific was developed based on the Precautionary Approach² and the protection and preservation of marine environments and included areas of particular environmental interest, which are to be preserved (Christiansen et al. 2022). However, as of today, environmental goals and objectives are only to be found in this REMF, which includes conservation objectives only for a specific geographical region (Amon et al. 2022; Tunnicliffe et al. 2020).

Overarching goals, objectives, targets, and indicators are still missing from the broader ISA environmental policy (including the Mining Code), preventing ISA from carrying out its mandate to protect the environment (Christiansen, Braeger, and Jaeckel 2022). To fulfill its environmental stewardship mandate, ISA needs to adopt a comprehensive strategic environmental management approach with strategic environmental objectives at its core, applicable to the whole Area (Ginzky, Singh, and Markus 2020; Jaeckel 2020; Tunnicliffe et al. 2020). This strategic approach to environmental management will also allow for the implementation of the Precautionary Approach, which is a direct obligation of international environmental law³ and requires ISA to favor caution and act preemptively to protect the environment from harm, even in the presence of uncertainties (Jaeckel 2020; Levin, Amon, and Lily 2020). Following Jaeckel (2020), Tunnicliffe et al. (2018), and other studies, we believe that the first step to a strategic approach to environmental management is the definition of Strategic Environmental Goals and Objectives (SEGOs). Defining

² The Precautionary Approach states that lack of scientific certainty cannot be used as a reason not to take measures to protect the environment.

³ For a review of the application of the Precautionary Approach in international environmental law see De Sadeleer, Nicolas. "The Principles of Prevention and Precaution in International Law: Two Sides of the Same Coin?" In *Research Handbook on International Environmental Law*, edited by Malgosia Fitzmaurice, Marcel Brus, Panos Merkouris, and Agnes Rydberg. Edward Elgar Publishing, 2021. <https://doi.org/10.4337/9781786439710.00015>.

SEGOs would fill the gap between the granular environmental management (i.e., contractor level) as it is presently embodied in the ISA regulations and the strategic environmental management (i.e., ISA level) that ISA's environmental stewardship mandate requires (Ginzky, Singh, and Markus 2020; Jaeckel 2020).

In this memorandum, we discuss two policy options for introducing SEGOs into the ISA's regulatory framework.

III. Policy options

SEGOs have been defined in several international fora, in close relation to sustainable development (Tunncliffe et al. 2020). SEGOs adopted by ISA should be long-term and generalizable across geographic space and resource type. As such, the two policy options we recommend in this memorandum are the following:

i. Policy option 1: Conduct a Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA) of mining activities in the Area.

SEAs are systematic processes for evaluating and addressing environmental consequences of proposed sectoral policies, plans, or programs (Sadler and Verheem 1996). SEAs are well suited to equip the ISA regulatory framework with SEGOs, as they encourage the definition of environmental objectives during sectoral policy-making activities (Wood and Dejeddour 1992), and are well equipped to address cumulative and long-term effects (Craik and Gu 2019).

A SEA for the Area should have broad stakeholder engagement and provide a framework to define SEGOs linked to targets measurable by performance indicators, from a consideration of ecosystems pressures and sensitivities, considering existing activities and cumulative effects on a long-term basis, as suggested by Tunncliffe et al. (2020). SEGOs would be linked with regional and project-level assessments via REMPs and project-level assessment requirements (i.e., the Environmental Impact Statement) respectively, thereby closing the gap between the strategic and the granular environmental management. Limitations of this option are that:

- ISA lacks environmental expertise and workload capacity to undertake SEAs
- ISA lacks a stakeholder engagement mechanism, including a response strategy to stakeholder input.

ii. Policy option 2: Adopt the integrated environmental assessment framework of the EU Marine Strategy Framework Directive (MSFD)

Integrated ecosystem assessments are cross-sectoral instruments that address the whole range of activities in the area concerned. SEGOs are defined in the early scoping phase of integrated environmental assessments, guiding what to assess, together with indicators and targets to measure the environmental status of ecosystems. Orejas et al. (2020) analyzed several integrated environmental assessment frameworks that potentially address the Area and concluded that the MSFD framework to assess the Good Environmental Status – which means the environmental status of marine waters where these are clean, healthy and productive, and the use of the marine

environment is at a level that is sustainable⁴ – could be transferred to the Area. The advantage of this policy option is that it would be faster than option 1 as the MSFD Good Environmental Status Descriptors, which are qualitative descriptors used to assess Good Environmental Status, would be adapted to the Area, i.e. become SEGOs, thereby reducing the time needed to define SEGOs compared to the time needed to carry out the SEA in policy option 1. Limitations of this option are:

- The MSFD framework is not designed specifically for deep-sea mining activities in the Area.
- Some of the Good Environmental Status Descriptors may not be adaptable at all or only partially adaptable to deep-sea mining, which could leave important gaps in the strategic environmental management policy of ISA.
- There will be a lack of stakeholder engagement in the definition of SEGOs.

IV. Consequences of inaction

In the absence of SEGOs, set by the regulator that later translate to project-specific goals and objectives, contractors would be handed excessive discretion in the preparation and implementation of their respective Environmental Management Plans and in the definition of environmental goals and objectives at the project level (Singh 2021; Jaeckel 2020). Under such circumstances, ISA would not be able to conduct a proper and thorough evaluation of environmental plans, rendering assessment procedures a mere formality, leaving itself without tools to manage the environmental impacts of seabed mining above project-level (Jaeckel 2020). This risk is exacerbated by the failure of ISA to finish the Draft Exploitation Regulations before the end of the “two-year rule” deadline (i.e., July 2023) and the lack of a strategic environmental policy, which raises concerns about unregulated deep-sea mining going forward.

V. Policy recommendation

ISA needs to consider defining SEGOs, as well as accompanying indicators and targets, to manage the environmental impacts of deep-sea mining. To achieve this, we recommend policy option 1, where ISA conducts a SEA of the Area. The advantage of this option, with respect to option 2, is that it provides a clear framework for the definition of specific SEGOs for the environmental management of activities in the Area and, indeed, of a strategic environmental policy, involving stakeholders from the beginning. Moreover, the complementary legal regimes of the Area and of the High Seas, recognize the importance of protecting and conserving ecosystems. The SEA would align the SEGOs defined by ISA to the overarching environmental goals and objectives of the Biodiversity Beyond National Jurisdiction instrument (Christiansen et al. 2022). This would allow for a coherent environmental impact assessment framework in the Area Beyond National Jurisdiction which comprises the Area and the High Seas (Mendenhall et al., 2023).

Regarding the position of SEGOs in the overall ISA regulatory landscape, opinions differ but there seems to be a preference in the scientific community for a Strategic Environmental Management

⁴ Directive 2008/56/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 17 June 2008 establishing a framework for community action in the field of marine environmental policy (Marine Strategy Framework Directive) (Text with EEA relevance), 2008. , OJ L.

Plan (Jaeckel 2020; Tunnicliffe et al. 2020; Christiansen, Braeger, and Jaeckel 2022). The establishment of this plan would be enabled by the SEA if ISA follows policy option 1.

Our policy recommendation provides the framework for ISA to develop a strategic policy for the conservation of the deep-sea ecosystems in the Area, based on sufficient scientific knowledge and in congruence with its complementary instrument for the High Seas, allowing it to fulfill its environmental stewardship mandate.

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